

NOTES

Isolation and Identification of Palmitone from the Leaves of Lauraceae Plants (*Cinnamomum camphora* Sieb., *Neolitsea sericea* Koidz., *Lindera umbellata* Thunb.)

N. Hayashi and H. Komae

Few studies have been published on the isolation of symmetrical aliphatic ketones from the plant waxes. Channon and coworkers^{1,2} first reported the existence of two symmetrical ketones (palmitone and di-*n*-tetradecyl ketone) in the waxes of cabbage leaf cytoplasm. Recently, Wakayama³ reported the presence of palmitone and its alcohol (16-hentriacontanol) in the flower of lily of the valley.

The present communication reports the isolation of palmitone from the leaves of three Lauraceae plants. The ketone was isolated from the ether extracts of the leaves using column chromatography with *n*-hexane. The ketone has the following physical properties: white plates m.p. 84–85°, gas chromatography t_R 49 min (Apiezon grease at 270°), molecular formula $C_{31}H_{62}O$ (M^+ 450, Found: C, 83.05; H, 13.3%, Calc: C, 82.60; H, 13.78%), $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 2900, 2840, 1712, 1465, 1418, 1380 cm^{-1} (saturated aliphatic ketone), δ^{CDCl_3} 0.89 (6H, t, $\text{CH}_3\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$), 1.26 (52H, broad s, $\text{-CH}_2\text{-}$), 2.39 (4H, t, $\text{-CH}_2\text{-CO-CH}_2\text{-}$).

The absolute identification of higher aliphatic ketones have given great trouble on account of the very similar physical properties, and IR and NMR spectra. So the structure can be determined by mass spectrum. In the mass spectrum, both m/e 239 (base peak, α -fission to the carbonyl group) and 255 ions (49.5 per cent, β -fission, McLafferty plus one ion) were very useful for identification of the symmetrical aliphatic ketone. In addition to the ions, m/e 267 (12.4%, γ -fission) and 281 ions (3.7%, δ -fission) were also found in the spectrum. On the other hand McLafferty plus 14 ions⁴ which has been found to be an important fragmentation of aliphatic ketones at low voltage (10–20 eV) was not observed in this spectrum (70 eV).

The ketone was finally identified as palmitone by preparing the authentic specimen¹. It seems reasonable that the symmetrical aliphatic ketones are very widely distributed in the plant kingdom. In the ketonic fraction palmitone was the main constituent and no other constituents were detected in this investigation.

Department of Chemistry,
Faculty of General Education,
Hiroshima University,
Hiroshima, Japan.

Received September 14, 1970

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